

SDIO SPACE INSULATION TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract - During the last five years the Strategic Defense Initiative Organization (SDIO) has performed a number of experiments, called Space Power Experiments Aboard Rockets (SPEAR), to understand the interaction of directed energy and kinetic energy systems with the low-earth-orbit (LEO) environment. The first experiment, SPEAR I, launched in December 1987, was designed to understand the formation of the plasma sheath around the spacecraft at high potentials up to 12 kilovolts. SPEAR I demonstrated that lightweight, high voltage systems could be operated in LEO without volume discharge and surface flashover by properly designed exposed high voltage surfaces. The SPEAR II program was designed to validate the space vacuum insulation technology by exposing two separate systems to the LEO environment. A 100 kV high voltage system and a 150 kA high current system were successfully tested in vacuum chambers without significant breakdown. New simulation models were developed which extended the Paschen breakdown curves to the LEO altitudes to include the effect of the geomagnetic fields. At this time, work is proceeding in the SPEAR III experiment which is planned for launch in early 1993. In SPEAR III, four grounding schemes will be tested for spacecraft charging levels up to about 4 kilovolts as a function of altitude and geomagnetic field orientation. Additionally, SPEAR III will test the effect of grounding techniques on the operation of solar cells.

Introduction

On March 23, 1983, President Ronald Reagan presented to the nation a plan to create an organization which would be responsible for the protection of the U.S. and its allies against a ballistic missile attack. The Strategic Defense Initiative Organization (SDIO) was formed in 1984. Since its inception, SDIO has been responsible for a large body of research leading to the development and testing of numerous systems. Two major classes of systems emerged from this work: kinetic energy and directed energy systems. Some of the kinetic energy systems first considered by SDIO were electromagnetic launchers, coil guns, and electrothermal guns. Some of the directed energy systems included neutral particle beams, space-

based free electron lasers, ground-based lasers, laser radar, charged particle beams, and high power microwaves [12]. These systems have one thing in common - they require the use of pulsed power systems to generate high voltages (hundreds of kilovolts) and/or high currents (hundreds of kiloamps) in periods less than a few milliseconds.

To understand the operation of such systems in low earth orbit (LEO) SDIO developed two sounding rocket programs, Beam Experiments Aboard Rockets (BEAR) and Space Power Experiments Aboard Rockets (SPEAR) [7,10]. The BEAR sounding rocket payload flight was designed to demonstrate that a neutral particle beam accelerator can be operated during space flight. The SPEAR Program was designed to investigate innovative techniques of using high power systems in space. The BEAR payload flight on July 13, 1989 collected information on the operation of neutral particle beam accelerator systems on spacecraft, spacecraft charging due to the ejection of charged beams, and on the near-field propagation of neutral beams in the upper atmosphere. The BEAR Program did not address the operation of a high power system in the LEO environment or the use of the ambient plasma as an insulator; the power system on the BEAR rocket payload was completely enclosed in a pressurized section isolated from the upper atmosphere.

The Space Power Experiments Aboard Rockets (SPEAR) were designed to establish the basis for treating problems in the areas of high voltage insulation and to develop and deploy pulsed power systems that make use of the space vacuum as the insulating medium [1]. Since the LEO environment is not a vacuum but is actually a low density gas or plasma; this ambient plasma causes problems in exposed spacecraft components and systems. Specifically, SPEAR addresses problems of electrical breakdown, power drain, outgassing, component operation, and spacecraft charging. Measurements made in the Defense Meteorological Satellite Program (DMSP) indicate spacecraft charging values as high as -1.4 kV [3]. These problems must be understood to prevent voltage breakdown in the ambient plasma for the proper operation of some of the SDIO systems.

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The SPEAR Program was divided into two efforts. The first effort was designed to investigate the interaction of the spacecraft with the environment [7]. It included measurements of the effects of outgassing and effluents on current collection and breakdown. The first part of this program, SPEAR I, was conducted during 1987. Questions raised during the SPEAR I effort are being addressed now in the SPEAR III effort. The second effort, SPEAR II, a much more complex program, looked at the actual operation of minimum insulation high voltage systems directly exposed to the LEO ambient plasma [3]. Before the SPEAR experiments are described, the conditions prevalent in the LEO environment and the problems related to operation of power systems in the ambient plasma are briefly presented.

Electrical Insulation in Space

High voltage and high current power systems require electrical insulation to avoid breakdown and discharge [9]. Ground systems currently use solid, liquid (dielectric oil), and gaseous insulation techniques; however, placing these systems in space requires light weight insulation techniques. Of the traditional ground insulators only electronegative gases appear to be light enough for use in space, but the containers needed to hold the various components and gases are large and heavy.

Therefore, SDIO has been investigating the use of vacuum (ambient plasma) as an insulator in LEO [7]. The LEO environment is a weakly ionized plasma with properties which vary as a function of time of day, latitude, and geomagnetic field. This ambient plasma is automatically replenished and does not deteriorate with time or with breakdowns, as do solid, liquid, and enclosed gas insulators. Furthermore, this plasma contains charged particles, electrons and ions, in addition to neutral molecules and atoms present in laboratory vacuum systems. Some of the difficulties introduced by the presence of charged particles for exposed power system components include: current drain from the ambient environment which reduces the efficiency of exposed high power components; breakdown between components, and between the ambient environment and the components which can disable them. The magnitude of these problems depends on the placement of the components and the plasma characteristics. [11]

During the SPEAR program, measurements were performed to characterize: 1) breakdown due to the grounding of the power system to the ambient plasma; 2) surge mechanisms causing surface flashover, gap breakdown,

and volume breakdown; and 3) current drain of the power components to the space environment. Results of some of these measurements are available in several documents.[7,2] Here, an analysis is presented to generalize to the space environment the Paschen law for breakdown voltage between two parallel electrodes under DC conditions. [8]

The Paschen breakdown theory is based in the Townsend theory of breakdown,[3] a current-voltage relationship, that is,

$$I = \frac{I_0 e^{\alpha d}}{1 - \gamma(e^{\alpha d} - 1)} \quad (1)$$

where I_0 is the initial current
 γ is the secondary emission coefficient
 d is the separation between electrodes, and

$$\alpha = f(V, pd) \quad (2)$$

for breakdown, the denominator in equation (1) becomes zero at a voltage V_B which is a function of pressure and distance,

$$V_B = V_B(pd) \quad (3)$$

Figure 1 shows the relationship between V_B and the pressure distance product, pd , and is known as the Paschen curve.

Fig. 1 Breakdown voltage, V_B , as a function of ambient pressure times the distance between the electrodes

The Paschen curve is only applicable to breakdown between two parallel plates. For more generalized geometries such as two concentric spheres, the voltage breakdown becomes influenced by the presence of magnetic fields. If the field strength is strong enough to substantially increase the mean electron path length above the mean free path, breakdown can occur.

Thus, for the complex geometries and environments such as the ambient plasma in the LEO environment, the Paschen curve can be generalized as shown in equation 4 to include the effect of the magnetic field,

$$V_B = V_B(B_p, pd) \quad (4)$$

and the corresponding Paschen curve as a function of magnetic field is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2 Breakdown voltage as a function of the magnetic field for varying pressures

where a critical magnetic field B_c separates the breakdown region. B_c is the lowest value of the magnetic field below which there will be no breakdown regardless of the pressure and voltage applied.

The generalized Paschen curve in the presence of the ambient plasma can be used to estimate the size of the sheath around a charged spacecraft. The size of the sheath can be measured by performing a pressurized chamber experiment with a variable magnetic field and a cylinder charged at a given potential representing the spacecraft. In the LEO environment the charged spacecraft in a plasma

generates a sheath of opposite charge which cancels the electrostatic field away from the spacecraft. Before the spacecraft is introduced to the plasma, the sheath is neutral with an equal amount of ions and electrons. [6] With the introduction of a negatively charged spacecraft, the electrons near the negative surface are expelled out and an ion sheath is created. [4] The first SPEAR experiment was developed to understand these spacecraft charging and discharging mechanisms.

SPEAR I

In December 1987, a space experiment was flown on a suborbital rocket flight from Wallops Island, Virginia to measure the effects of the ionospheric plasma on highly biased conductors [1,2,7]. SPEAR I charged two 20 cm diameter gold plated aluminum spheres above 40 kV to determine the electron current collected from the ionosphere at altitudes up to 370 km. A diagram of the payload is shown in Figure 3. A capacitor was discharged through the sphere with a time constant of 1 sec achieving potentials on the sphere between 5 and 46 kV. If an electrical breakdown occurred, large current spikes would be recorded in the sphere current probe.

During the suborbital experiment no electrical breakdowns occurred above 110 km. The current collected from the sphere was linear to the applied voltage at a rate of 1.43 mA/V. At the maximum voltage of 46 kV, the spacecraft floated negatively to about 12 kV creating two plasma sheaths. An ion collecting sheath surrounding the spacecraft and an electron collecting sheath surrounded the spheres. The sheath interactions were simulated using the NASCAP-LEO and POLAR codes. Substantial outgassing of the payload occurred, and the pressure at the skin surface was about three orders of magnitude higher than the ambient pressure.

The experiment showed that spacecraft surfaces can be charged to approximately -10 kV without detectable system effects. Even though, the actual use of vacuum as an insulator in practical systems has to be addressed in practical systems, i.e., SPEAR II, the SPEAR I experiment showed no major problems in the use of space insulation.

Fig. 3. SPEAR I Payload

SPEAR II

The fundamental element of the SPEAR II program was the concept of replacing the normal insulation required by high power systems on the Earth's surface by the ambient plasma of the LEO environment. This concept can lead to a marked reduction in the weight and volume of insulation required for high power space systems. The SPEAR II program attempted to develop the specific components and systems needed in a power system which is exposed to the LEO space environment.

SPEAR II consisted of two experiments, high voltage and high current, both using minimally insulated components exposed to the LEO ambient plasma. [3] The high voltage experiment consisted of a Klystrode, and used a voltage up to 100,000 volts with an electron beam section of an actual RF tube serving as the load. The tube

was a prototype of tubes that could be used in future accelerator systems. The circuitry included pulse forming networks and a transformer, which produced a nominal power pulse of one megawatt. The high current experiment had an electromagnetic railgun launcher as the load. This device operated at a current of 150,000 amperes, accelerated a projectile down its barrel and into space at a high velocity. The power conditioning circuit included a high energy density capacitor bank storing 15 kJ, a high charge transfer switch, high power crowbar diode and an exposed storage inductor. Figure 4 shows the high voltage and high current components of the SPEAR II payload and the load objectives. Some of the components were in an enclosed environment and some were exposed to the ambient plasma. The actual payload configuration is shown in Figure 5. The left side of the photograph shows the exposed components which were: the 100 kV voltage probe, the railgun, the Klystrode, the pulse transformer, the pulse forming networks, and the pulse shaping inductor.

Fig. 4 The SPEAR II System Block Diagram

HIGH VOLTAGE SYSTEM:

Fig. 5. SPEAR II Payload

The SPEAR II payload was operated at the approximate gas pressure and plasma density expected at LEO in the NASA/Plum Brook large vacuum chamber. The design, fabrication, modeling and testing, efforts resulted in new knowledge in design and operation of high voltage space systems. The results of the program can be

categorized by components produced and new analysis and testing capabilities. Table 2-1 provides a summary of the major accomplishments in component design. Table 2-2 summarizes the new design, analysis and testing capabilities produced.

Table 2.1
 Significant Innovative Contributions From
 SPEAR II: Components

Product	Main Features
Battery Pack	Lightweight (95 lb), compact (2 cu.ft), 6 kV,60 kW, 450 kJ, prime power source qualified to withstand Aries rocket launch vibration and shock levels. The modular, fault tolerant design emphasized reliability and personnel safety.
Energy Storage Capacitors	Energy storage capacitors qualified to withstand Aries launch shock and vibration levels.
Rotating Arc Gap Switch	Compact, lightweight, triggerable, sealed, high current, high Coulomb transfer switch.
Crowbar Switch	Rugged, compact, lightweight, solid state switch with high peak current and coulomb transfer capabilities.
High Voltage Bushings	Novel, resistive bushings which eliminate dielectric surface flashover as the limiting factor for high voltage applications in vacuum and LEO plasma environments.
Pulse Forming Network Inductors	Inductors which can operate while exposed to the LEO environment. The designs minimize the electric field stresses on dielectric surfaces and prevent the ionization of background gas by electrons trapped in the magnetic field.
Pulse Transformer	Lightweight, high reliability, open frame design for high voltage (100 kV), repetitive (50 pulses per second) operation. The design minimizes potential surface flashover paths and facilitates rapid outgassing of the transformer windings.
Storage Inductor	Space vacuum-insulated, lightweight, high current storage inductor designed for small fringing magnetic fields and therefore minimal perturbation of the surrounding plasma.
Rail Gun	Lightweight design using a composite barrel structure. The busswork was designed to minimize the possibility of dielectric surface flashover.
Klystrode	Existing Klystrode design was modified to allow operation with the device exposed to the LEO environment. This resulted in substantial weight savings for space-based applications.
High Voltage Probe	100 kV voltage divider designed for operation in the LEO environment.
Fiber Optics Cable	Fiber optic transmission system modified to operate without arcing in a vacuum near high voltage components.
Optical Imaging System	Optical imaging system which used coherent fiber optics to view high voltage and high current systems while allowing the video and still cameras to be located well away from these systems.
Pulse Counting Photometer	Fiber optic-coupled, pulse counting photometer which achieved a 200 ns time resolution through pulse mapping techniques.
Load Conditioning Vacuum Chamber	Lightweight, flyable vacuum chamber which could withstand static and dynamic forces during launch, allow exposure of the payload to the LEO environment and protect the payload during reentry.
Data Acquisition and Telemetry Systems	Spacecraft data acquisition and telemetry systems designed to withstand unprecedented levels of electromagnetic interference from high voltage and high current systems.
Electro-optic Electric Field Probe	Extremely compact, lightweight, broad bandwidth electric field probe suitable for any environment, including LEO.

Table 2.2
 Significant Innovative Contributions From SPEAR II:
 Design, Analysis, and Testing Capabilities

Product	Main Features
Mock-Up Tests	Inexpensive, fast turnaround component and payload mock-ups which provided valuable space simulation chamber testing data early in the payload development.
Gas Distribution Models	Outgassing and gas flow models were incorporated into a modeling package which gave the gas pressure in various payload regions as a function of time and predicted high voltage breakdown.
Outgassing of Spacecraft Materials	Studies of the short-term outgassing properties of numerous spacecraft materials as a function of several parameters. These studies provided important data for high voltage breakdown predictions.
Plasma Interaction Codes	Computer codes which allowed the analysis of dynamic plasma interactions with complex, three dimensional geometries representing the high voltage payload.

The exposed insulator surfaces used in SPEAR II were made to be slightly conductive rather than insulative since this would prevent charging of the insulator surface. Another cause of surface insulator breakdown is electron impact induced charging. This problem was solved by placing conducting fins at regular intervals along the insulating structure. In addition to reducing the surface charge and thus preventing electron impact, the fins provide capacitive grading for the insulator which enhances the high frequency performance and provides barriers which interrupt any developing surface discharges. In addition, two of the main accomplishments listed in Tables 2-1 and 2-2, the Fiber Optic Cable for remote positioning of the optical imaging system, and the Pulse Transformer are particularly innovative and worthy of description.

Optic Fiber Cable:

The low level light camera needed to be placed remotely from the exposed power system components because of potential damage from the high-voltage environment and to provide isolation to reduce the possibility of conducted destructive emissions from the load section to the telemetry encoders and electronics. [see Chapter 5 in reference 3] The fiber optical bundle needed to be enclosed in order to protect the delicate fibers and to provide a hard mounting surface. Typically a stiff continuous shield would be used, but this presented a potential arcing and discharge path as well as a source of gas which would reduce the level of vacuum around the payload. In order to solve these issues, a two-part bundle enclosure was developed. The entire length of fiber optic bundle was wrapped in a loosely-braided fiberglass sheath. This protected the fibers during ground handling and yet allowed any trapped gas to quickly escape. This sheath was too flexible to

provide a hard mounting surface, so two inch long stiff teflon sleeves were installed in one foot intervals inside of the fiberglass sheath. These stiff teflon sleeves allowed the cable to be mounted securely while still providing for release of trap gas during ascent.

Pulsed Transformer

The pulse transformer was designed by the Westinghouse Science and Technology Center (WSTC) in Pittsburgh, Pa [see Chapter 4 in reference 3]. The transformer was required to step up the input voltage from the three Pulse Forming Networks (PFNs) from 6 kV to 100 kV for a step up ratio of 16.7:1. The output of the pulse transformer was applied to the cathode of the Klystrode, a gridded RF tube which served as the high voltage system load. The transformer has to deliver pulses at a repetition rate of 50 pulses per second and a power level as high as 1 MW, i.e. 10 A at 100 kV.

In order to design the transformer to use the ambient plasma as an insulator, numerous innovative steps were taken. A summary of the major steps made by WSTC were:

- (1) The transformer secondary was wound in tapered slots on etched Teflon insulator cards.
- (2) The slots in the cards were made sufficiently deep so that the conductors and the triple junctions (the common junction of the conductor, the insulator, and the vacuum) were completely beneath the surface of the Teflon; the conductors were exposed only where they passed from one card to another.
- (3) The thicknesses of the Teflon cards was varied with the voltages between turns on adjacent cards, that is, the higher the voltage, the thicker the card.
- (4) The electric field in the vicinity of critical triple junctions was

kept low through the use of stainless steel spinnings/shields. (5) The high radial electric fields were restricted to the vacuum gap between the spinnings and adjacent low voltage structures. (6) The gas pressure in the interior of the transformer was kept low by allowing trapped gas to escape from the transformer interior, and by placing adjacent teflon cards touched only at small snubber areas. Figure 6 shows the transformer secondary winding.

Fig. 6 SPEAR II Transformer Secondary Winding

The SPEAR II payload was successfully operated before the flight in a simulated LEO environment. Unfortunately, the final verification of the proper operation of the SPEAR II system in the LEO environment did not take place. The flight attempt took place on July 25, 1990 at the White Sands Missile Range. The Ariès rocket carrying the SPEAR II payload suffered a guidance system malfunction and began to roll approximately 15 seconds into the flight, veered off course and had to be destroyed. Nonetheless, since the payload had been successfully operated in a number of chamber tests exposed to a simulated LEO atmosphere, the design configuration has been largely validated.

The specific details of the SPEAR II high power system can be found in the book, SPEAR II High Power Space Insulation. [3]

SPEAR III

SPEAR III will compare the effectiveness of different grounding techniques as a function of altitude in LEO, attitude relative to the geomagnetic field, and various voltage levels, and will answer most of the questions raised by the SPEAR I experiment. SPEAR III will examine the role of effluents in the grounding processes and validate effluent distribution models and also study the effects of spacecraft charging and discharging on solar cell performance.

The SPEAR III payload will have only one sphere which will be charged to a maximum voltage of 20 kV with two different time constants. A time constant of one second will simulate abrupt charge in the spacecraft whereas a time constant in the order of 100 seconds will simulate lower potentials and rising spacecraft charging. The Sphere shown in Figure 7 will be biased positively relative to the payload by onboard batteries. This will drive the payload negative with respect to the ambient plasma. Figure 7 shows a schematic of the SPEAR III payload which is being built by Utah State University for a 1993 launch date.

Fig. 7 SPEAR III Payload

The following four techniques will be used to discharge the spacecraft: plasma contactor, neutral gas release, heated thermionic emitter, and field emission devices. In the plasma contactor, neutral gas is released to a discharge chamber. The magnetic field and ionization filament in the chamber produces plasma which is released out of the spacecraft. Then, the subsequent flow of additional gas out of the chamber will produce a cascade reaction of charged particles to discharge the spacecraft. In the neutral gas release, ions are created in a cascading fashion to discharge the spacecraft. In the heated thermoionic emitter, power is applied to a heated thermionic emitter when the spacecraft is charged and electrons will be emitted out of the spacecraft to neutralize the spacecraft charging. Finally in the field emission devices, power is turned on to create a potential between the metal tips and the metal gate films releasing electrons to neutralize the spacecraft.

The SPEAR III experiment will also examine the role of effluents in the grounding process and the distribution of effluents around the vehicle. Several measurements will be performed. A spectrometer will be used to measure spectra of discharge plumes near the vehicle.

Data will be collected on discharge duration, location, effluent origin, distribution, composition and plasma parameters. A high sensitivity, gated low light level TV will be used to record output of spectra. Various gases will be released from the various subsystems to determine the effect of effluents. Finally, internal measurements will be performed to determine the magnitude and shape of transient pulses in the internal spacecraft wiring. If fully successful, the SPEAR III experiment will increase significantly our understanding of the interaction between a spacecraft and the LEO environment.

Conclusion

A conclusion so far from these experiments is that the ambient plasma can allow breakdown and that specific design practices can inhibit this breakdown. The ambient plasma is enhanced by material outgassing, trapped gases, and spacecraft produced effluents. A number of studies of voltage breakdown in spacecraft systems from test and flight experience have been performed [13]. However, the ambient plasma conditions cannot be easily simulated on vacuum chambers and some uncertainties exist trying to verify vacuum chamber results by launching a payload to low-earth-orbit.

Large potentials generated by spacecraft charging can cause systems or subsystem failures in spacecraft, and spacecraft grounding techniques must be developed. The results of the SPEAR I and III experiments are being used to understand spacecraft charging mechanisms and grounding techniques. During SPEAR I the spacecraft was charged to a maximum of 12 kV without breakdown. From the four techniques being investigated for spacecraft grounding only the plasma contactor has been previously used. In the plasma contactor the required discharge chamber and the storage of the gas makes the technique heavy, and voluminous. The other techniques being investigated—neutral gas release, thermionic resistor, and field emission devices—require less weight, volume, and power; but these techniques have to be fully demonstrated before they become practical. Additionally, the introduction of effluents from the attitude control system and from operational systems in the spacecraft affect the grounding mechanism. The SPEAR III experiment will provide additional measurements in the spacecraft charging and discharging process and the effect of effluents.

SPEAR II measured the performance of two systems, a high voltage and a high current experiment. These experiments simulated the behavior of the typical systems that could be operated in space; the railgun high current system and the neutral particle beam high voltage system.

A portion of these systems was designed to operate open to the ambient plasma. These systems were operated in small chambers and in the large NASA Plum Brook vacuum chamber. To make the components operate properly in the vacuum chamber, many design changes were incorporated. A summary of the component changes was presented in this paper together with a more detailed description of specific changes in two of these devices—the pulse transformer and the optical fiber cable. These type of examples are very important because they provide the designer with some of the engineering guidelines required for the design of spacecraft power systems.

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